

I. Title:

The White *Pleurotus Djamor* Mushroom as a Potential Additive in Nutraceutical Products Based on In-Vitro Evaluation of its Antioxidant and Non-Cytotoxic Properties

II. Abstract

This study aimed to establish the white variant of *Pleurotus djamor* collected from the wild in Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, as a potential natural additive for nutraceutical products and safe to be taken as a food resource, based on in-vitro evaluation of its antioxidant and non-cytotoxic properties. Using the mushroom's methanolic extract (*Pleurotus djamor* Methanolic Extract or PDME) and ethanolic extract (*Pleurotus djamor* Ethanolic Extract or PDEE), this study determined the antioxidant properties of the mushroom based on Total Phenolics Content (TPC), Percentage of Radical Scavenging Activity (% RSA) and Reducing Power Capacity (RPC). The non-cytotoxic properties of both extracts were determined through the brine shrimp lethality assay. Results revealed that both extracts have remarkable antioxidant properties. The PDME yielded a TPC value of 31.08 mg/g GAE, 69.72% RSA, and 0.217 RPC. The PDEE yielded a TPC value of 25.67 mg/g GAE, 68.81% RSA, and 0.299 RPC. Both mushroom extracts are non-toxic with an LC₅₀ of 2,678.42ppm. The study finds that the white variant of *P. djamor* used in this study is a potential natural antioxidant additive for nutraceutical products and is safe to be utilized as a food resource.

Keywords: antioxidant, cytotoxicity, mushroom, nutraceuticals

III. CNS Research Agenda: Health, Natural Products

IV. Proponents:

1. ARLENE L. TABAQUERO
2. CATHELYN C. MARIANO
3. JOAN B. TAROMA

Research Assistants:

1. HANSON T. VILLANUEVA
2. GABRIELLE CHRISTOPH ERAÑA
3. JARYL KATE T. DINAMLING
4. REGIDOR ALMENDRAL

V. Mechanism applied for: D

VI. RATIONALE

One of the research agenda of the Center for Natural Sciences (CNS) of Saint Mary's University (SMU) is to explore on biological resources which can be utilized in the formulation of natural products such as food supplements, nutraceuticals and alternative medicines. Mushrooms have been one of the biological resources considered by the CNS in this research agendum. For these mushrooms to be fully evaluated of their potentials, Tabaquero, Mariano, Aceret, Villanueva, Dalog and Dinamling (2019) initiated a revival the mushroom technology in the Center, as a follow through of the Fabelico (2011) study. The revival initiative focused on the most efficient spawns to be used to yield good quality mushrooms. Aside from the objective of bringing economic-friendly returns by using the innovative methods of spawn production, the study also was an initial step for the realization of a full mushroom production in the CNS. However, there are some pending projects as to the built of well-equipped mushroom facility, hence production and extension of the technology to recipient communities to help them come up with additional source of income through mushroom growing, are not feasible at the moment. While waiting for resources for a full blown mushroom production to operationalize in the CNS, researches (Almendral & Aceret, 2019; Quilban & Aceret, 2019) were encouraged with focus on *Pleurotus* species. To carry out the agendum of the CNS on the formulation of natural products, this study was done to unveil potentials of *Pleurotus* mushrooms and may later be the species to be included for mass production when full blown mushroom operations will be done in the CNS.

Mushrooms are good sources of protein and polysaccharides, making them recognized as important food items of nutritional values and therapeutic properties (Atila, 2017). Among those of the about 3000 edible mushrooms are the *Pleurotus* spp. which contain various types of vitamins and amino acids, high content of fiber and protein and low fat content (Chang & Miles, 2004). The health benefiting effects they possess include anticancer, antihyperlipidemic, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial activities, anti-mutagenic, anti-allergic and cardioprotective effects (Atila,

2017; Ahmad, Mahmood, Khalil, Zamir, Fazal, & Abbasi, 2014; Nedelkoska, Pancevska, Amedi, Veleska, Ivanova, Karadelev et al., 2013).

One of the *Pleurotus* species which have been studied to contain several compounds that contribute to its diverse benefiting properties is the *Pleurotus djamor* (Leal, Mendez, Castro & Zapata, 2010; Sasidhara & Thirunalasundari, 2014; Ragasa, Tan, Ting, Reyes, Brkljača. and Urban, 2016;). Taxonomically there are three reported varieties of this species: var. *djamor*, var. *roseus* and var. *cyathiformis* (Lechner, Wright & Alberto, 2004; Guzman 2000). The white varieties are the *Pleurotus djamor* (Fr.) Boedijn var. *djamor* and the *Pleurotus djamor* var. *cyathiformis* Corner (Saha, Acharya, & Roy, 2012; Lechner, Wright & Alberto, 2004). Their difference is on the pileus, wherein the var *djamor* has a spathulate to flabelliform pileus while the var. *cyathiformis* has a cyathiform pileus (Lechner, Wright & Alberto, 2004; Guzman 2000). The *Pleurotus djamor* var *roseus* Corner is the pink variety and it is commonly called pink oyster mushroom or salmon-pink mushroom (Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan, & Raaman, 2014; Ragasa, Tan, Ting, Reyes, Brkljača & Urban, 2016; Ragasa 2018).

In one of the fieldworks conducted by the faculty and students of the Center for Natural Sciences, they were able to collect a white mushroom in Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya. Local folks have informed that the mushroom is being consumed as food. It is known to them as *tiblak*. This mushroom was grown in vitro by Almendral and Aceret (2019) using formulation liquid substrates from fruit peels. The mushroom was also studied for its antibacterial and teratogenic effects on zebra fish and was molecularly identified as *Pleurotus djamor* in the study of Quilban and Aceret (2019). From these two studies, the present study aims to unveil the potentials of the mushroom in terms of its antioxidant and non-cytotoxic properties for possible inclusion of the mushroom in the production of nutraceuticals and to further establish it as safe to be utilized as food resource.

VIII. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to evaluate in-vitro the antioxidant and non-cytotoxic properties of the *Pleurotus djamor* collected from the wild in Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya. Using the mushroom's methanolic (*Pleurotus djamor* Methanolic Extract or PDME) and ethanolic extract (*Pleurotus djamor* Ethanolic Extract or PDEE), the following are the specific objectives of the study:

1. To determine the antioxidant properties of the PDME and PDEE based on:
 - a. total phenolic content (TPC)
 - b. percentage of radical scavenging activity (%RSA)
 - c. reducing power capacity (RPC)
2. To determine the non-cytotoxic properties of the PDME and PDEE based on % mortality and LC₅₀ value.

IX. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The antioxidants of synthetic origin have been proposed for use in the treatment of various free radicals related diseases but the commercialized synthetic compounds have toxic effects (Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan, & Raaman, 2014). Hence, antioxidants from natural food and plant extracts have been pushed in researches to find for their applications in pharmaceuticals and alternative medicines. Among the natural foods that are promising on these aspects are mushrooms. Several *Pleurotus* mushroom species have antioxidant (Ribeiro, Rangel, Valentao, Baptista, Seabra & Andrade, 2006; Cheung, Cheung & Ooi, 2003;)and hypertension and cholesterol lowering activities (Jegadeesh, Raaman, Hariprasath, Ramesh & Srikumar, 2014; Hasan, Khatun, Sajib, Rahman, Rahman, Roy, Miah & Ahmed, 2015; Hossain, Hashimoto, Choudhury, Alam, Hussain, Hasan, Choudhury, Mahmud, 2003).

Based on the review paper of Adebayo and Oloke (2017), *Pleurotus* species are commercially important in the world mushroom market. It is widely cultivated and consumed in different parts of the world. Many people admire the mushroom due to its taste, flavor, high nutritional values, and some medicinal properties. *Pleurotus* are generally rich in proteins with essential amino acids, physiologically important polysaccharides and essential fatty acids, dietary fibers, important minerals, and some vitamins. The presence of some bioactive substances, majorly polysaccharide-protein complex in the genus *Pleurotus* has been reported to confer some pharmacological potential such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammation, anti-hypercholesterolemia, anti-hypertensive, anti-diabetic, hepato-protective and anti-allergic activities. The high nutritional value and potential medicinal uses suggest that the oyster mushrooms are pharmacologically important as functional foods.

Though a good number of *Pleurotus* species have already been reported for their antioxidant and anti-cytotoxic effects, there are a lot more of species which have incomplete data along these lines, especially the mushrooms which are found in the wild and are claimed by local residents in the area as

edible and medicinal. One *Pleurotus* mushroom that has been found by the CNS team in one of their fieldwork activities is the *P.djamor* which was found growing in rotten logs in the mountains of Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya. It has been recently evaluated for the best liquid media that can support its mycelial growth (Almendral & Aceret, 2019) and its identity has been molecularly established, along with its antibacterial and teratogenic activities (Quilban & Aceret, 2019). To complete its bioactive profile and further established its potential for processing as a natural food supplement, this study will work on its antioxidant and non-cytotoxic properties.

This study is guided by the paradigm as shown below. The collected white *P. djamor* mushroom was analyzed for its antioxidant properties and non-cytotoxic properties. These screening methods established the mushroom to be safe for human in-take (anti-cytotoxic) and can possibly be processed in the nutraceutical and biology-based industries as an alternative to synthetic antioxidants or as a possible natural food resource. In these ways, this study finds its significant contribution in the attainment of the research agendum of the CNS on health and natural products. The results are added parameters in considering the realization of full-blown mushroom production operations in the Center which can provide services to the Center's recipient communities and small-scale mushroom growers in the province to help them come up with additional source of income through mushroom growing.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm

X. SCOPE AND DELIMITATION

This study used only the white variety of *P. djamor* mushroom collected from the wild, particularly in the mountains of Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya. Methanol and ethanol solvents were used in producing the extracts (PDME & PDEE) which were tested for both antioxidant and non-cytotoxic properties. The screening for antioxidant properties is limited to the quantification of Total Phenolics Content (TPC), Percentage of Radical Scavenging Activity (%RSA) and Reducing Power Capacity (RPC). The non-cytotoxic properties evaluation was based on the computed % Mortality and LC50 value using brine shrimp lethality assay.

XI. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is significant to generate awareness in public of the possible health benefits of *P. djamor* which was collected from the wild in the mountains of Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya. It provides the local folks in the area with the the profile of the said mushroom as to its safe utilization for food.

This study also leads the way to pharmaceutical or nutraceutical and biology-based industries to further processed the mushroom as natural antioxidant or as a possible additive in nutraceutical products.

Since this study presents the health benefits of *P.djamor*, this study also provides benefit to *Pleurotus* mushroom growers. They can add the said mushroom in their mushroom growing business.

This study will generate interest among researchers, particularly the mushroom enthusiasts, to scout for other edible *Pleurotus* mushroom species which can be found in the wild and have them evaluated of their health benefits.

XII. DEFINITION OF TERMS

Antioxidant Properties – It refers to the capability of the mushroom extract to inhibit oxidation as measured by total phenolics content, percentage of radical scavenging activity and reducing power capacity.

Total phenolic content (TPC) - It refers to the amount of phenolic compounds in gallic acid equivalent (GAC) present in the mushroom quantified through spectrophotometric analysis.

Percent radical scavenging activity (%RSA) - It refers to the capacity of the mushroom extract to scavenge radicals as its antioxidant potential, measured through spectrophotometric analysis using 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging method.

Reducing power capacity (RPC)- It refers to the strength of the extract to reduce another substance as measured by absorbance readings in spectrophotometric analysis.

Non-cytotoxic Properties – It refers to the characteristics of the mushroom as safe and edible for consumption by not causing death to the hatched nauplii in the brine shrimp lethality assay. The non-cytotoxic properties include computations for percent mortality and LC₅₀ value.

XIII. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Conceptual Literature

The mushroom *Pleurotus djamor*

Three varieties of *Pleurotus djamor* have been reported in literature. These are the var. *djamor*, var. *roseus* and var. *cyathiformis*. The *Pleurotus djamor* (Fr.) Boedijn has been reported as the white ecological variety found in the northern tropical moist deciduous forests of Tripura, India where it is a common vegetable to tribal of Tripura due to much palatability and other culinary purposes, used as substitute for soybean or egg (Saha, Acharya & Roy, 2012). Another white variety is the *Pleurotus djamor* var. *cyathiformis* Corner, but has a cyathiform pileus, differentiating it from the spatulate to flabelliform pileus in var *djamor* (Lechner, Wright & Alberto, 2004). The pink variety is the *Pleurotus djamor* var. *roseus* Corner. It has also spatulate to flabelliform pileus but as the name implies, it is pinkish in color (Lechner, Wright & Alberto, 2004; Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan, & Raaman, 2014; Selvakumar, Rajasekar, Babu, Periasamy, Raaman & Reddy, 2015; Ragasa, Tan, Ting, Reyes, Brkljača & Urban, 2016; Ragasa 2018). It was further described by Jegadeesh, Lakshmanan, Kab-Yeul, Sabaratnam, Raaman (2018) as an edible mushroom, with pink sporophore, large sized fruit bodies and delicious flavor; and can be grown at 26°C and 35°C and with relative humidity above 80%. The taxonomic descriptions of these varieties are presented in Lechner, Wright and Alberto (2004).

Antioxidant Properties of Mushrooms

The antioxidant potential observed in mushrooms is part of their natural defense mechanism against noxious events causing oxidative damage (Jeng-Leun, Hsiu-Ching & Chin-Chu, 2002). Mushroom species show antioxidant capacity in *in vitro* systems (Ribeiro, Rangel, Valentao, Baptista, Seabra & Andrade, 2006) and are found to be rich in antioxidant activities using methanol and water extracts (Cheung, Cheung & Ooi, 2003). Evaluating their antioxidant properties are done through quantification of phenolic compounds (Saha, Acharya & Roy, 2012), determination of 1, 1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging activity and reducing power (Ramkumar, Ramanathan, Thirunavukkarasu & Arivuselvan, 2010; Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan & Raaman, 2014). These methods are also being utilized by the CNS in the assessment of antioxidant activities of plant samples, mushrooms and mycobionts.

Antioxidant compounds prevent oxidative damage related to aging and diseases, such as atherosclerosis, diabetes, cancer and cirrhosis (Khan *et al.*, 2010). Mushrooms are generally rich in vitamins A, C and E, carotenoids, flavonoids and other simple phenolic compounds, which are proven to prevent oxidative damage and thus protect the human body (Ren *et al.*, 2014). Also, mushrooms produced variety of secondary metabolites, which have been shown to act as excellent antioxidants (Woldegiorgis *et al.*, 2014). The phenolic compounds in mushrooms are excellent antioxidants and synergists, but are not mutagenic (Yildiz, Can, Laghari, Sahin, & Malkoç, 2015). The reported effects are mainly associated with the antioxidant properties of phenolic compounds due to redox reactions, which allow them to act as donors of hydrogen atoms or as reducing agents (Ahmad, Mahmood, Khalil, Zamir, Fazal & Abbasi, 2014). Free radicals, according to Ramkumar, Ramanathan, Thirunavukkarasu and Arivuselvan (2010), are responsible for aging and causing various human diseases. The antioxidant substances scavenge these free radicals and hence prevent the occurrence of free radical-induced diseases. By donating hydrogen radicals, the primary radicals are reduced to non-radical chemical compounds and are then converted to oxidize antioxidant radicals. This action helps in protecting the body from degenerative diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, immune-system decline, brain dysfunction and cataracts. In general, the consistent antioxidant activities reported in literature by the *Pleurotus* spp. may be due to high phenol, flavonoid and other antioxidant phytochemicals present in the mushroom extracts (Patel *et al.*, 2012).

Non-cytotoxic Properties of Mushrooms

Mushrooms offer variety of health benefits. They are low calorie food with very little fat and are highly suitable for obese persons (Jegadeesh, Raaman, Hariprasath, Ramesh & Srikumar, 2014) as they reduce the serum cholesterol in human bodies which reduces hypertension (Hasan, Khatun, Sajib, Rahman, Rahman, Roy, Miah & Ahmed, 2015). They are ideal materials for the dietetic prevention of atherosclerosis, due to their high content of fiber, proteins, microelements, and their low fat content (Bae, Sinha, Park, Song, Yun, 2000). The *Pleurotus* species or the oyster mushrooms are an ideal dietary substance for the prevention and treatment of hypercholesterolemia due to high content of dietary fiber, sterol, proteins, and microelements (Hossain, Hashimoto, Choudhury, Alam, Hussain, Hasan, Choudhury, Mahmud, 2003).

With some of the mentioned health benefits of mushrooms, it is important to establish their non-cytotoxic properties for an evaluation of how safe they can be for consumption or in-take, especially those collected from the wild. The brine shrimp lethality bioassay is very utilitarian to evaluate the bioactivity of the mushroom extracts (Moreira et al., 2007) and the LC50 value which can be computed from the analysis reveals cytotoxic strength (Haque, Rana, Aktar, Haque, Chouduri, Islam, 2016).

Research Literature

In the study of Saha, Acharya and Roy, (2012), *Pleurotus djamor* (Fr.) Boedijn. procured from northern tropical moist deciduous forests of Tripura (India) was found to contain 1.2-2.7 mg/g of total phenols on the fresh weight basis. Quantitative estimation of total phenols and antioxidants (viz., FRAP, SOD and POX) revealed that the species showed highest amount of phenols and antioxidants in juvenile bud stage (one day stage) and gradually decreased, but at post-mature (four days old) condition, amount of total phenol again increased. This present study also revealed that *Pleurotus djamor* is also a good source of antioxidants such as FRAP, SOD and POX in fresh condition.

Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan, and Raaman (2014) determined the *in vitro* antioxidant and antibacterial activities of five different (petroleum ether, hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate and fractionized methanol extract) fractions from the crude methanolic extract of an edible mushroom *Pleurotus djamor* var. *roseus* (GenBank database, Maryland, USA–Accession number GU350628). Five different fractions were screened for antioxidant potential by three different assays viz., ferric thiocyanate (FTC), thiobarbituric acid (TBA) method and (DPPH) free radical-scavenging assay and antibacterial activity against clinically important bacterial strains *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 2079), *Bacillus cereus* (ATCC 11778), *Escherichia coli* (ATCC2567), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (ATCC 29665) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 2036) determined by well diffusion method. Results indicated that the fractionized methanol and hexane fractions of *P. djamor* var. *roseus* exhibited both antioxidant and antibacterial activity. Hexane extract exhibited strong antioxidant activity with an IC50 value of 2.7 mg/mL followed by methanol extract (IC50-2.862 mg/mL). FTC and TBA tests showed strong inhibition of lipid-oxidation in hexane fraction evident from its low absorbance value compared to other fractions. The total phenolic content was high in the fractionized methanol extract (2.25 mg/g GAE) followed by hexane extracts (0.35 mg/g GAE). Hexane extract exhibited maximum zone of inhibition against the test pathogenic bacteria followed by fractionized methanol extract. The present study showed that five different solvent fractions of *P. djamor* exhibited varying antioxidant and antibacterial activities. Further, this edible mushroom may be a potential source of natural antioxidants and antibacterial agents.

The study of Jegadeesh, Raaman, Hariprasath, Ramesh and Srikumar (2014), highlights the efficacy of edible mushroom *Pleurotus djamor* var. *roseus* extracts on total cholesterol, low density lipoprotein (LDL), very low density lipoprotein (VLDL), High density lipoprotein (HDL) and free fatty acid in experimentally induced hypercholesteromic rats. Five group of rats were employed which includes control, mushroom extract, hypercholesterolemia rats (4 % cholesterol + 1% cholic acid + egg yolk), hypercholesterolemia rats treated with Mevinolin and hypercholesterolemia rats with pretreatment of mushroom extract and each group includes six animals. Results from the study showed that significant increase in the total cholesterol, LDL, VLDL and free fatty acid observed in hypercholesteromic feed rats were significantly reduced in mushroom extract treated hypercholesteromic rats. These results suggest that mushroom supplement provided health benefits by acting on the lipid profile in hypercholesterolemic rats.

In the review conducted by González, Saldívar, and Uribe (2017) on the nutritional composition and nutraceutical properties of the *Pleurotus* fruiting bodies, several recent studies on hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effects were mentioned for *P. eryngii*, *P. sajor-caju*, *P. abalonus*, and *P. ostreatus* but further

studies are required to evaluate the interactions among the *Pleurotus* polysaccharides and statins to reduce cholesterol levels.

As cited in Ragasa, CY. (2018), there are several compounds reported to have been found in *P. djamor* (pink mushroom) such as anthroquinones, flavonoids, phenols, saponins, tannins, and terpenoids with reports on the protein, ash, and fat contents from Leal, Mendez, Castro, and Zapata (2010). The antioxidant property of the mushroom extract was attributed to the presence of phenols and flavonoids (Sasidhara& Thirunalasundari, 2014). In the chemical investigation of Ragasa, Tan, Ting, Reyes, Brkljača. and Urban (2016) of the dichloromethane extract of *Pleurotus djamor*, the following were isolated: ergosterol (1), triacylglycerols (2), and fatty acid methyl esters (3). The structures of 1-3 were identified by comparison of their NMR data with literature data.

The study of Almendral and Aceret (2019) evaluated the type of liquid media that can produce the highest mycelial biomass yield of the white variant of *P. djamor* collected from the wild in the mountains of Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya. Different growth conditions were considered. Six fruit peels were chosen to serve as sources of formulated liquid substrates: banana, cassava, citrus, coconut, papaya and potato. Mean mycelial yield served as the basis in the determination of the best liquid medium and consequently, the best medium was utilized for the determination of the optimal culture conditions which were the following: pH, illumination and temperature. Results led to the papaya liquid medium with the highest sugar content to have the highest mean mycelial yield. In the evaluation of optimal culture conditions, pH 8, dark condition, and 23°C - 25°C under an air-conditioned set-up were observed to have promoted the highest mean mycelial yields.

In the study of Quilban and Aceret (2019), the identity of the variant of *P. djamor* used in Almendral and Aceret (2019), was established through molecular analysis. Screening for its bioactivities that could possible establish the mushroom as a potential for cancer treatment was also done through phytochemical screening, antibacterial assay and teratogenic test using zebra fish. Results revealed the presenrce of essential oils, higher alcohols, steroids, phenols, fatty acids, sugars, anthraquinones, coumarins, anthrones, tannins, flavonoids and alkaloids. It was found to be an active inhibitor for the growth of *Escherichia coli* but has a partially active antibacterial capability when tested against *Pseudomans aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Teratogenic effects were observed in the development of zebra fish as shown by malformations induced under the 1000, 100 and 10 ppm concentrations of the mushroom extract.

Synthesis

The studies cited above are generally of the pink variant of *P. djamor*. Only a few have been studied for the white variant. Since the mushroom collection in the CNS utilized in the study of Almendral and Aceret (2019) and of Quilban and Aceret (2019), is the white variant, this study aims to unveil more the potentials of this locally available mushroom found in Kayapa, Nueva Vizaya, with the parameters which were not covered in the two cited studies, such as the antioxidant properties and cytotoxic properties.

XIV. METHODOLOGY

Collection and culture of *Pleurotus djamor*

Fruiting bodies of white *P. djamor* were collected from Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya. These were subjected to extracting procedures to carry out the laboratory tests for antioxidant and cytotoxicity.

Preparation of the *Pleurotus djamor* mushroom extract (PDME & PDEE)

Using the maceration method of extraction (Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan, & Raaman, 2014; Jegadeesh, Raaman, Hariprasath, Ramesh & Srikumar, 2014), the fruiting bodies of the mushroom *P. djamor* were air dried, powdered (coarse, 1000 g) and were soaked in methanol and ethanol separately (1:10) for 72h at room temperature. Each of the mixtures were filtered and the filtrate were concentrated on a rotary evaporator at 45C. The filtrates were labeled as *Pleurotus djamor* Methanolic Extract (PDME) and *Pleurotus djamor* Ethanolic Extract (PDEE) which were both used for antioxidant and cytotoxicity tests.

Determination of antioxidant properties of *Pleurotus djamor*

Quantification of total phenolic content

Total phenolic content was determined using the methods (with modifications) in Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan, and Raaman (2014) and Sunita & Dhananjay (2010). The amount of total phenolic in the extracts was determined with the Folin- Ciocalteu reagent. Gallic acid was used as a standard and the total phenolic content was expressed as mg/g Gallic Acid Equivalents (GAE). Concentration of 31.25, 15.63, 7.81, 3.91, 1.95, 0.98, 0.49 and 1 mg/ml of gallic acid were prepared in methanol (for PDME) and in ethanol (for PDEE). Concentration of 1mg/ml of PDME and 1mg/ml of PDEE were also prepared in methanol and ethanol respectively and 0.5ml from each of these were introduced into test tubes separately and mixed with 2.5ml of a 10-fold dilute Folin- Ciocalteu reagent and 2ml of 7.5% sodium carbonate. The tubes were covered with parafilm and allowed to stand for 30 minutes at room temperature before the absorbance was read at 760 nm spectrophotometrically. Spectrophotometric readings were performed in triplicate. The calibration curve was constructed with different concentrations of gallic acid (0.01 mM to 0.1 mM) as standard. Total phenolic compounds was quantified from the calibration curve ($y = 2.9671x + 0.0199$, $R^2=0.9761$) of gallic acid standard. The total phenolic content was expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE) in mg/g extract.

DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) free radical scavenging activity

The methods (with modifications) by Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan, and Raaman (2014) and Kolak, U., Osturk, M., Ozgokce, F., & Ulubelen, A. (2006) were followed in this study. Separate preparations for PDME and PDEE were made. The concentrated extract (PDME or PDEE) was used to make a stock solution and aliquot was taken to make 1000ppm dilution and 1000ppm of Catechin as control (1mg/mL). Then, 1mL of prepared stock solution were mixed with 4 mL of 0.1mM DPPH solution in separate plastic cuvette. Reactions were done in triplicate. The prepared mixtures were incubated in the dark at 37°C for 30 minutes. The absorbance readings were monitored at 517 nm using Spectrum lab 752s UV VIS Spectrophotometer. The ability to scavenge the DPPH radical was calculated using the formula: % Radical Scavenging Effect = $[(A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}}] \times 100$, where A_{control} is the absorbance of the control which is the DPPH without the test sample, A_{sample} is the absorbance of the test sample containing the mixture of the DPPH and the sample. Catechin was used as the positive control. A lower absorbance of the reaction mixture indicated higher free radical scavenging activity. The radical scavenging activities were compared to the activity of the control Catechin.

Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Test

The reducing power using the Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) Test was determined following the methods used in Ramkumar, Ramanathan, Thirunavukkarasu and Arivuselvan (2010). A volume of 2.5 mL of PDME or PDEE was mixed with 2.5 mL of 200 mM sodium phosphate buffer and 2.5 mL of 1% potassium ferricyanide and the mixture was incubated at 50°C for 20 min. After 2.5 mL of 10% trichloroacetic acid was added, the mixture was centrifuged at 650 rpm for 10 min. The upper layer (5 mL) was mixed with 5 mL of deionised water and 1 mL of 0.1% ferric chloride and the absorbance was measured at 700 nm in a spectrophotometer. A higher absorbance indicates a higher reducing power. Absorbance readings were compared to that of ascorbic acid as the standard positive control.

Determination of non-cytotoxic effects

The Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BSLA) was conducted based on the methods (with some modifications) of Meyer *et al.*, (1982), Oloa and Nuñez (2013) and Haque, Rana, Aktar, Haque, Chouduri and Islam (2016). Artificial seawater was prepared by dissolving 3.8g of sea/rock salt in 100mL of distilled water for hatching the shrimp eggs. The artificial seawater was put in a standard size of petridish (hatching chamber) with a partition for dark (covered) and light areas. Shrimp eggs were added into the dark side of the chamber while the other side (light) served as area to attract the hatched shrimp. Two days were allowed for the shrimp to hatch and mature as nauplii (larva). After two days, when the shrimp larvae were ready, 1 mL (1000ppm, 500ppm, 250ppm, 125ppm and 62.5ppm) of the mushroom extract (separate preparations for PDME and PDEE) was added to each 15 well plates using 24 well plates and 10 brine shrimps were introduced into each well. This set up was done in triplicate. Thus, there were a total of 30 shrimps per dilution. The well plates were left uncovered under the light/lamp. The number of dead shrimps were counted and recorded after 24 hours. Using Probit Analysis, the lethality concentration (LC_{50}) was assessed at 95% confidence intervals. LC_{50} of less than 1000 ppm was considered as potent (active). As mentioned by Meyer *et al.*, (1982), LC_{50} value of less than 1000 ppm is toxic while LC_{50} value of greater than 1000 ppm is non-toxic. The mean mortality was also calculated by adding the

number of dead nauplii per replicate divided 3 (replicate). This is to ensure that the death (mortality) of the nauplii is attributed to the bioactive compounds present in the extracts.

Treatment of Data

The results of this study were analyzed and interpreted descriptively as done in most studies of similar nature (Haque *et al.*, 2016).

XV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Antioxidant Properties

The antioxidant properties of the PDME and PDEE are shown in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Table 1:

Total phenolic content of the mushroom extracts in GAE per mg of sample

Sample Description	Equation for Gallic Acid Standard Curve		Gallic Acid Equivalent (mg/g)
	$y = 0.0048x + 0.0718$ (where y = mean absorbance)		
PDME	0.221		31.08
PDEE	0.195		25.67

Table 2:

Radical scavenging activity (%) of the mushroom extracts and Catechin as standard

Sample Description	Absorbance Reading			Mean Absorbance	% Radical Scavenging Activity (RSA)
	1	2	3		
PDME	0.065	0.068	0.066	0.066	69.72%
PDEE	0.069	0.066	0.070	0.068	68.81%
Catechin (standard)	0.038	0.040	0.039	0.039	82.11%

Abs DPPH = 0.218; Wavelength 517 nm using Spectrum lab 752s UV VIS Spectrophotometer

Table 3:

Reducing power capacity of the mushroom extracts and the controls based on absorbance readings

Sample Description	Absorbance Reading			Mean Absorbance @700 nm
	1	2	3	
PDME	0.217	0.216	0.218	0.217
PDEE	0.299	0.298	0.301	0.299
Distilled Water (- control)	0.026	0.025	0.027	0.026
Ascorbic Acid (+ control)	0.493	0.452	0.497	0.481

In Table 1, it is shown that the total phenolic content (TPC) of both extracts quantified from the calibration curve ($y = 0.0048x + 0.0718$) of gallic acid standard, yielded to results of a higher GAE for PDME (31.08 mg/g GAE of sample) than PDEE (25.67 mg/g GAE sample). This shows that both extracts indeed contain phenolic compounds which support further the results in Table 2 and Table 3 that *Pdjamor* exhibit sufficient protective mechanisms towards radicals and reactive species of certain chemicals.

These obtained TPC values are evidently higher than those obtained in *P. djamor* species in other studies such as 13.22 mg/g in TPC assay (Puttaraju, Venkateshaiah, Dharmesh, Urs, Somasundaram, 2006), 1.2-2.7 mg/g on fresh weight basis (Saha, Acharya & Roy 2012), 2.25 mg/g GAE in the fractionized methanol extract and 0.35 mg/g GAE in hexane extract (Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan & Raaman, 2014). The presence of phenols makes the mushrooms gain antioxidant properties (Leal, Mendez, Castro, and Zapata, 2010; Sasidhara & Thirunalasundari, 2014; Ragasa, 2018) and so are excellent antioxidants and synergists, but are not mutagenic (Yildiz, Can, Laghari, Sahin, & Malkoç, 2015). Phenolic compounds have been found to have antioxidant activity in the inhibition of low density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation (Jegadeesh, Hariprasath, Kumaresan & Raaman, 2014) and are responsible in radical scavenging activities (Mau *et al.*, 2002; Wasser, 2002) to prevent oxidative damage and thus protect the human body (Ren *et al.*,

62.5ppm	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
LC ₅₀								2678.42

LC50 – the concentration needed for the sample to cause 50% mortality

Results show that for PDME, deaths have been observed starting at 15 hours under 1000ppm (10%) and at 18 hours (0.67%) at 500ppm. In PDEE, mortality rate is observed only at 1000ppm at 18 hours (10%). Increasing mortality rate is observed in both concentrations in the succeeding observation hours from the onset (15 hours for PDME and 18 hours for PDEE), only after 6 hours (21 hours for PDME and 24 hours for PDEE). No deaths have been observed in the lower concentrations.

The computed LC50 for both mushroom extracts is 2,678.42 ppm. This means that in 24 hours, the concentration of mushroom extract must be 2,678.42 ppm in order for it to cause death for half (50%) the total brine shrimp population. This is already a very high concentration and since it is above 1000ppm, both extracts are found to be non-toxic, based from Meyer *et al.*, (1982) interpretation.

In summary, both PDME and PDEE extracts exhibit antioxidant and non-cytotoxic properties. Based from the evaluations done, the *P. djamor* used in this study is safe as a food resource and is a potential additive for nutraceutical products.

XVI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The white variant of *P. djamor* collected from the wild in Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya utilized as food by the local folks, is safe as a food resource and is a potential antioxidant additive for nutraceutical products. It is recommended to conduct a study on the formulation of a nutraceutical product containing *P. djamor* as an additive.

XVII. REFERENCES

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